

Eliminating Noise in the Matrix Profile

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Abstract: As companies are increasingly measuring their products and services, the amount of time series data is rising and techniques to extract usable information are needed. One recently developed data mining technique for time series is the Matrix Profile. It consists of the smallest z-normalized Euclidean distance of each subsequence of a time series to all other subsequences of another series. It has been used for motif and discord discovery, for segmentation and as building block for other techniques. One side effect of the z-normalization used is that small fluctuations on flat signals are upscaled. This can lead to high and unintuitive distances for very similar subsequences from noisy data. We determined an analytic method to estimate and remove the effects of this noise, adding only a single, intuitive parameter to the calculation of the Matrix Profile. This paper explains our method and demonstrates it by performing discord discovery on the Numenta Anomaly Benchmark and by segmenting the PAMAP2 activity dataset. We find that our technique results in a more intuitive Matrix Profile and provides improved results in both usecases for series containing many flat, noisy subsequences. Since our technique is an extension of the Matrix Profile, it can be applied to any of the various tasks that could be solved by it, improving results where data contains flat and noisy sequences.

1 INTRODUCTION

The amount of data available as time series is rapidly increasing. This increase can be explained by the lowering cost of sensors and storage, but also due to the rising interest of companies to gain new insights about their products or services. Areas of interest include pattern discovery (Papadimitriou and Faloutsos, 2005), anomaly detection (Wang et al., 2016) and user load prediction (Vandewiele et al., 2017).

The Matrix Profile is a recently developed data mining technique for time series data that is calculated using two time series and a single intuitive parameter: the subsequence length m . It is a one-dimensional series where each data point at a given index represents the Euclidean distance between the z-normalized (zero mean and unit variance) subsequence starting at that index in the first time series and the best matching (lowest distance) z-normalized subsequence in the second time series. Both inputs can be the same, meaning matches are searched for in the same time series, in this case a trivial match buffer prevents the subsequence matching itself or nearby neighbours. The Matrix Profile Index, which is calculated alongside the Matrix Profile, contains the index of the best match for each subsequence.

The Matrix Profile can be used for motif discovery (finding the best matching subsequence in a series), discord discovery (finding the subsequence with the largest distance to its nearest match) or as a building block for other techniques such as segmentation, visualizing time series using Multidimensional Scaling (MDS) (Yeh et al., 2017b) or finding gradually changing patterns in time series (Time Series Chains) (Zhu et al., 2017). The Matrix Profile has been applied to various topics, including medical signals (Yeh et al., 2016), query logs (Zhu et al., 2017) and music (Yeh et al., 2017a).

The original STAMP algorithm is able to calculate the Matrix Profile in $O(n^2 \log n)$ time and $O(n)$ memory (Yeh et al., 2016). It uses the fact that the z-normalized Euclidean distance between two vectors can be calculated in constant time, given the dot product of those two vectors, it calculates these dot products using the MASS algorithm (Mueen et al., 2015), based on the Fast Fourier Transform. The later developed STOMP algorithm further improves this runtime to $O(n^2)$ by reusing intermediate results.

A number of features/advantages of the Matrix Profile are:

- The only required parameter is the subsequence length m , which has a clear meaning for users;

Figure 1: Top: Three pairs of sequences with varying slopes but exactly the same amount of noise. Bottom: The z-normalized versions of the same sequences. We see how depending on the slope, the Euclidean distance greatly varies between the z-normalized sequences due to the amplification of the noise. The z-normalized Euclidean distances are (from left to right): 7.61, 3.55 and 1.81.

- The runtime to calculate the Matrix Profile is independent of the chosen subsequence length m ;
- Using the STAMP algorithm, a very accurate guess of the Matrix Profile can be made in a fraction of the time needed to calculate it;
- The algorithms to calculate the Matrix Profile are well suited for parallelization, as has been demonstrated in a GPU implementation (Zhu et al., 2016);
- The Matrix Profile is not based on heuristics and always provides an exact solution;
- No assumptions are made about the data, making this technique domain agnostic.

Although z-normalization is important when comparing time series (Keogh and Kasetty, 2002), there is one major downside: on a *flat* signal, any fluctuations (noise) on the signal are enhanced, resulting in high values in the Matrix Profile. We demonstrate this in Figure 1: we created 3 pairs of sequences, each consisting of two lines having a specific slope. Each pair has the exact same amount of noise added to both lines. Despite the original sequences being equally distant, the z-normalized sequences have a lower distance on the sloped lines. Since the Matrix Profile uses the z-normalized Euclidean distance, it is also affected by this phenomenon.

Most use cases in literature relating to the Matrix Profile focus on processing time series where flat sequences are rare or indicate periods of (uninteresting) inactivity, these are not negatively affected by this phenomenon. On the other hand, cases where flat patterns are relevant will suffer from the influence of noise. As a preliminary example, observe Figure 4. Here, we see a discord that is not picked up by the Matrix Profile due to the noise in the flat areas of the signal. We discuss this example in detail in Section 4.

Generally, the effects of flat sequences might result in misleading or plain wrong insights. This is problematic, since in many realistic cases a flat sequence can occur and might simply indicate a steady regime of the underlying process. Some cases and their respective periods of flat signals are: seismology (periods of seismic inactivity), system monitoring (similar metrics during a long running task - used in Section 4) and movement monitoring (periods of inactivity - used in Section 5). To improve the results of the Matrix Profile for these kinds of cases, we investigated and analytically estimated the influence of noise on the Matrix Profile, allowing us to negate it.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 lists literature related to the Matrix Profile. In Section 3 we explain how to eliminate the effects of noise. Section 4 demonstrates the effect of our technique on anomaly detection for a simple synthetic example and using data from the Numenta Anomaly Benchmark (NAB). In Section 5 we apply our technique to time series segmentation on passive activities using the PAMAP2 dataset (Reiss and Stricker, 2012). We conclude our findings in Section 6.

2 RELATED WORK

In this section we focus on related work specifically about the Matrix Profile.

The original Matrix Profile paper (Yeh et al., 2016) introduces the Matrix Profile as a new method for finding similarities in one-dimensional time series, which can also serve for motif and discord discovery as a side effect. The authors explain the STAMP and STAMPI algorithms to calculate the Matrix Profile in batch and incremental steps respectively, based on the MASS algorithm (Mueen et al., 2015). A later paper (Yeh et al., 2017a) extends the Matrix Profile to be able to work with multi-dimensional data.

The STOMP algorithm, a faster version of STAMP that reuses intermediary results in its calculation, is introduced in (Zhu et al., 2016). The same paper describes how a GPU-based version of STOMP (GPU-STOMP) was used to calculate the Matrix Profile on a seismology dataset of 100 million datapoints in only 12 days.

Yeh et al. describe how MDS, a data exploration technique, does not work well when considering the subsequences in a time series (Yeh et al., 2017b). Instead, it is useful to select representative subsequences to use as input for MDS. When dealing with discrete time series, the selection can be done using the Minimum Description Length (MDL) and Reduced Description Length (RDL), effectively se-

lecting subsequences that provide good compression. The authors find that the Euclidean distance is a good proxy for RDL in real-valued time series, and can be used to select the salient subsequences for display in MDS, meaning the Matrix Profile can be used for this task.

Sometimes the findings of the Matrix Profile do not coincide with the interests of the user, as they might be interested in specific time frames, highly variable patterns or in regions coinciding with activity in another time series. Using a user-defined Annotation Vector, introduced in (Dau and Keogh, 2017), a user can modify a Matrix Profile, putting more focus on the regions that he is interested in.

Time Series Chains are defined in (Zhu et al., 2017) as slowly changing, repeated patterns in time series. To find them, they define the left and right Matrix Profile, containing the distance to the best earlier and later subsequences. They are calculated using a modified version of STOMP that has the same complexity.

The Matrix Profile Index can be used to perform time series segmentation: dividing a time series in internally consistent regimes (Gharghabi et al., 2017). By examining the arcs defined by the matches found by the Matrix Profile, they explain how a lower-than-expected number of arcs at a specific timestamp gives an indication of a change in the underlying system. Their FLUSS algorithm and its online variant FLOSS are found on average to outperform human segmentation, based on experiments with 22 subjects and 12 data sets.

The Matrix Profile has been used for various techniques and applied to data from various domains. However, data where flat and noisy subsequences are present has been mostly avoided in Matrix Profile related literature, most likely due to the issue introduced in Section 1. In fact, we suspect this issue will negatively affect many applications of the Matrix Profile, severely limiting its applicability. To the best of our knowledge, no technique has been published so far to tackle the negative effects of flat and noisy subsequences. In the following section, we will elaborate on this issue and provide a solution for it.

3 ELIMINATING NOISE

In this section, we present our contribution: a way to remove the effects of noise from the Matrix Profile. In Section 3.1, we first estimate the effect of noise when calculating the z-normalized Euclidean distance between identical sequences. Next, we present how to use this estimate in the calculation of the Matrix Pro-

file in Section 3.2. Finally, we discuss the complexity of the resulting algorithm in Section 3.3.

3.1 Estimating the Influence of Noise

In this section we will estimate the amount of noise affecting the Matrix Profile using statistical methods. By taking this estimate into account while calculating the Matrix Profile, we will be able to greatly reduce the influence of noise.

Assume we have a base sequence $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ and derive two sequences \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} by adding Gaussian noise \mathbf{N}^1 and \mathbf{N}^2 that was sampled from a normal distribution with variance σ_N^2 .

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{S} &= (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_m) \\ \mathbf{X} &= (s_1 + n_1^1, s_2 + n_2^1, \dots, s_m + n_m^1) \\ \mathbf{Y} &= (s_1 + n_1^2, s_2 + n_2^2, \dots, s_m + n_m^2)\end{aligned}$$

Ideally, we would want the Euclidean distance between \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} to be zero, since they are both (noisy) measurements of the exact same sequence \mathbf{S} . Remember that the Matrix Profile uses the Euclidean distance of the z-normalized sequences.

$$\begin{aligned}D(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) &= \text{EucDist}(\hat{\mathbf{X}}, \hat{\mathbf{Y}}) \\ &= \text{EucDist}\left(\frac{\mathbf{X} - \mu_{\mathbf{X}}}{\sigma_{\mathbf{X}}}, \frac{\mathbf{Y} - \mu_{\mathbf{Y}}}{\sigma_{\mathbf{Y}}}\right) \\ &= \sqrt{(\hat{x}_1 - \hat{y}_1)^2 + \dots + (\hat{x}_m - \hat{y}_m)^2}\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

Here, $\hat{\mathbf{X}}$ denotes the z-normalized sequence, μ denotes the mean and σ the standard deviation.

We now determine the expected influence of the noise. From here on, we consider the sequences as random variables, and highlight this by referencing them as X and Y .

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}[D(X, Y)^2] &= \mathbb{E}[(\hat{x}_1 - \hat{y}_1)^2 + \dots + (\hat{x}_m - \hat{y}_m)^2] \\ &= m \cdot \mathbb{E}[(\hat{x} - \hat{y})^2] \\ &= m \cdot \mathbb{E}\left[\left(\frac{x - \mu_X}{\sigma_X} - \frac{y - \mu_Y}{\sigma_Y}\right)^2\right]\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

Since X and Y are the sum of the same two uncorrelated variables, they both have the same variance.

$$\sigma_X^2 = \sigma_Y^2 = \sigma_S^2 + \sigma_N^2 \quad (3)$$

Furthermore, we can decompose μ_X and μ_Y in the original μ_S and the influence of the noise. Here we use n as the random variable sampled from the noise distribution. Note that μ_S can be seen as a constant.

$$\begin{aligned}
\mu_X &= \mu_Y = \mu_S + \frac{n_1 + \dots + n_m}{m} \\
&= \mu_S + \mu_N \\
\mu_N &\sim \mathcal{N}\left(0, \frac{\sigma_N^2}{m}\right)
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

We can do the same for x and y , where s is an unknown constant:

$$\begin{aligned}
x &= y = s + n \\
n &\sim \mathcal{N}\left(0, \sigma_N^2\right)
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Using (3), (4) and (5) in (2), canceling out constant terms and merging the distributions results in:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}[D(X, Y)^2] &= m \cdot \mathbb{E}\left[\left(\frac{n_x - n_y - \mu_{N_x} + \mu_{N_y}}{\sqrt{\sigma_S^2 + \sigma_N^2}}\right)^2\right] \\
&= m \cdot \mathbb{E}\left[(v)^2\right] \\
v &\sim \mathcal{N}\left(0, \frac{2 + 2m}{m} \cdot \frac{\sigma_N^2}{\sigma_S^2 + \sigma_N^2}\right)
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Finally, we apply the theorem $\mathbb{E}[X^2] = \text{var}(X) + \mathbb{E}[X]^2$:

$$\mathbb{E}[D(X, Y)^2] = (2m + 2) \cdot \frac{\sigma_N^2}{\sigma_S^2 + \sigma_N^2} \tag{7}$$

We now have an estimate of the distance between two sequences that originate from the same sequence but have been contaminated by Gaussian noise. Note that in (7), σ_N^2 is the variance of the noise and $\sigma_S^2 + \sigma_N^2$ is the variance of the noisy sequence.

3.2 Algorithm for Noise Elimination

Implementing noise elimination is straightforward, we subtract the squared estimate from the original squared distance (e.g. as calculated by the MASS algorithm). We do this *before* the element-wise minimum is calculated and stored as value for the Matrix Profile, because this correction might influence which subsequence gets chosen as the best match. Pseudocode is listed below.

```

Input: d # distance between subsequences X, Y
Input: m # length of each subsequence
Input: std_X # standard deviation of X
Input: std_Y # standard deviation of Y
Input: std_n # standard deviation of noise

```


Figure 2: Time measurements show the overhead of the noise elimination, though the complexity remains $O(n^2)$.

```

d_corrected = sqrt(d^2 - (2 + 2m) * std_n^2 /
max(std_X, std_Y)^2)
return d_corrected

```

Note that the maximum of the standard deviation of both sequences is used. Given two fundamentally different subsequences, this choice effectively minimizes our estimate. We note that we tried other means of combining the standard deviations such as mean and minimum, but these produced similar results.

3.3 Complexity Analysis

The noise elimination is a constant operation if we know the standard deviations, so complexity remains $O(n^2 \log n)$ when using STAMP and $O(n^2)$ when using STOMP. This assumes the standard deviations for all subsequences are precomputed, as is the case in the STOMP and STAMP algorithms. A plot of the influence of time series length versus runtime is shown in Figure 2.

4 USE CASE: ANOMALY DETECTION

One of the original applications for the Matrix Profile was finding discords. Since discords are defined as the subsequences in a series that differ most from any other subsequence, they can be interpreted as anomalous subsequences. Since each Matrix Profile value represents the distance of each subsequence to its nearest match, the top discord can be found trivially given the Matrix Profile: it is the subsequence corresponding to the highest value. When interested in the top-k discords, one can take the top-k values of the Matrix Profile where each value should be at least m index positions away from all previous discord locations. Since overlapping subsequences are very similar in shape, this prevents selecting the same discord multiple times (Mueen et al., 2009).

In this section, we will use anomaly detection as use case to demonstrate the influence of noise on the Matrix Profile. We first focus on a small synthetic dataset to provide details and insights, after which we

Figure 3: Top: Sinusoid signal, an anomaly of length 10 was added at index 950. The top discord (containing the anomaly) and its closest match are highlighted in red and orange. (The top discord containing the anomaly starts at the highest value of the Matrix Profile.) Bottom: Corresponding Matrix Profile calculated with subsequence length $m = 150$. The effect of the anomaly stands out as a series of high values.

present results for real-world data from the Numanta Anomaly Benchmark (Lavin and Ahmad, 2015).

4.1 Synthetic Data

We start from a synthetic dataset of 2000 samples of a sinusoid in which we introduced an anomaly in one of the downward slopes by increasing the value of 10 consecutive samples by 0.5. The dataset and corresponding Matrix Profile can be seen in Figure 3. Here, we see how the Matrix Profile clearly highlights the subsequences containing the anomaly. For calculating the Matrix Profile, we used a subsequence distance m of 150 and a trivial match buffer of $\frac{m}{2}$, as recommended in (Yeh et al., 2016).

Next, we added Gaussian noise sampled from $\mathcal{N}(0, 0.01)$ and recalculate the Matrix Profile using the same parameters. The resulting dataset and corresponding Matrix Profile can be seen in Figure 4. Although we see still the impact of the anomaly in the Matrix Profile as a deviation in the pattern, it does not lead to a high value in the Matrix Profile. In a larger, more realistic dataset, this could mean that the anomaly would go unnoticed. Instead, the top-6 discords coincide with the flat sections of the sinusoid, where the noise has been upscaled due to the z-normalization. This is visualized in Figure 5, where we overlay the z-normalizations of the subsequences of the top discord and its best match with a subsequence containing the data anomaly and its best match. Since the Matrix Profile consists of the Euclidean distance between z-normalized subsequences, more erratic z-normalized subsequences will typically lead to higher distances.

After recalculating the Matrix Profile using our noise elimination technique from Section 3, the Matrix Profile again closely matches the Matrix Profile on the noise-free data, as can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 4: Top: Same signal as Figure 3, but with added Gaussian noise. The anomaly is highlighted in green. The top discord and its closest match are highlighted in red and orange, they do not contain the data anomaly. Bottom: The corresponding Matrix Profile, the effect of the anomaly is still visible but no longer stands out as a high value.

Figure 5: A close-up of the z-normalized subsequences explains why the top discord has a higher Matrix Profile value than any subsequence containing the data anomaly. The effect of the noise becomes larger due to the z-normalization when the original subsequence is “flatter”. Top: z-normalized subsequence of the top discord and its closest match (as marked in Figure 4). Bottom: z-normalized subsequence that contains the data anomaly and its closest match.

Most subsequences now have a distance of zero, indicating exact matches in the remainder of the series. The anomaly is again clearly visible and would be marked as the top discord. Lastly, we see some non-zero values not related to the anomaly, these are caused by locally higher-than-expected noise values in that part of the signal. It can be noted that these values depend on the sampling of the noise and can in fact be seen as subtle anomalies.

Let us briefly further investigate how the properties of the noise affect the Matrix Profile. Figure 7 displays our starting sinusoidal signal and anomaly, to which Gaussian noise sampled from different distributions was added. As expected, we see that as the variation of the noise increases, the anomaly becomes less apparent in the Matrix Profile. The anomaly is no longer visually obvious in the Matrix Profile for noise with variance of 0.25 or more. Somewhat surprising is how quickly this effect becomes apparent: when the noise has a variance of around 0.0004 (at this point the signal-to-noise ratio is 1250 or 31 dB), the anomaly is already occasionally overtaken as the top discord by

Figure 6: Plot of the Matrix Profile for the noisy data (blue), for noise-free data (dashed green) and for the noisy data, but with the noise elimination applied (orange). We see that the noise corrected Matrix Profile closely matches the Matrix Profile of the noise-free data.

Figure 7: Top: Sinusoid signal with anomaly to which Gaussian noise sampled from different distributions has been added. Bottom: Corresponding Matrix Profile calculated with subsequence length $m = 150$ for each of the noisy signals. We see how the Matrix Profile becomes less insightful as the amount of noise increases.

the flat subsequences (depending on the sampling of the noise). The noise cancellation technique becomes unreliable once the variation is around 0.0625, and is no longer useful for variations of 0.25 or higher. This can be explained by the subtlety of our anomaly (an increase by 0.5 for 10 time units), as high variance noise can create similar artifacts. Note that these insights are hard to generalize as a rule of thumb, as they really depend on the properties of the time series, the anomalies and the considered subsequence length.

Lastly, we discuss why some simple, seemingly useful methods to tackle the effects of noise are not generally usable.

- Changing the subsequence length m : as m becomes smaller, the effect of the anomaly on the Matrix Profile will indeed be bigger. However, the effect of the noise also becomes bigger, resulting in a more erratic Matrix Profile, still making it hard to find the actual anomaly. Without knowing in advance what one is looking for, it is hard to select a good value of m . This is demonstrated in Figure 8 (top).
- Ignoring flat sections: ignoring subsequences

Figure 8: Approaches for negating the effects of noise that do not work. Top: Matrix Profile using different values for the subsequence length m . Middle: Matrix Profile while ignoring subsequences with standard deviation below 0.2. Bottom: Matrix Profile after applying a Savitzky-Golay smoothing and a Wiener frequency filter to the noisy data.

whose variance is below a certain value would result in removing the peaks in the Matrix Profile. A first problem is finding the correct cut-off value, which is not trivial. Secondly, this approach would not be applicable in datasets where flat signals are the anomalies, or where matches on flat signals are useful, as is demonstrated in the time series segmentation of Section 5. This approach is demonstrated in Figure 8 (middle).

- Smoothing or filtering: by preprocessing the noisy signal, one could hope to remove the noise altogether. Unfortunately, unless the specifics of the noise are well known and the noise can be completely separated from the signal, there will always remain an amount of noise, resulting in the same effects. This is demonstrated in Figure 8 (bottom).

4.2 Numenta Anomaly Benchmark

The Numenta Anomaly Benchmark (NAB) is a collection of datasets, score metrics and supporting tools. Most datasets are from real-world applications in different domains and have been annotated by hand by multiple people and combined using a consensus method. The benchmark is aimed at real-time anomaly detectors, this is reflected in the scoring method, where *anomaly time windows* are defined and detection in the start of the window is better rewarded.

We limited ourselves to the “realAWScloudwatch” collection, because this collection was the only one that contained many flat, noisy time series. The collection consists of 17 datasets of real-world data, measuring computer workload such as cpu utilization, bytes written and request count. Each dataset spans a time period of 4 to 16 days sampled at 5 minute intervals and contains 0 to 3 anomalies. One

Figure 9: Plot of the “rds_cpu_utilization_cc0c53” dataset from the Numenta Anomaly Benchmark, it contains 2 anomalies (dots) with associated anomaly windows (red).

dataset with 2 anomalies is visualized in Figure 9.

We did not use the score metric of the NAB, as it requires labelling anomalies in a streaming fashion, which would require optimizing a classification threshold for the Matrix Profile. Instead, we relied on the inherent ordering of normal to anomalous subsequences that is captured in the Matrix Profile: We calculated the Matrix Profile over the time series and counted how many guesses were needed to find all anomalies, with a limit of 10 wrong guesses. Note that when calculating the Matrix Profile, we only used data from previous time steps to define normal behavior, this is in line with the real-time anomaly detection idea of the NAB and is needed to ensure we match their definition of anomalous behavior.

We compare the performance of the Matrix Profile with and without noise elimination. For each dataset, we set the subsequence length equal to half the anomaly time window (which is defined by the NAB as 10% of the data length, divided by the number of anomalies present). Furthermore, like in the NAB, we use the first 15% of the data as reference data and do not report any anomalies in it. For the noise elimination, we estimated the standard deviation of the noise as the 5th percentile of the standard deviations of all subsequences found in the reference data. This value was similar to a manually estimated value on a few test datasets and was selected as an easy, automatically derivable value. Note that we did not optimize the noise estimation value in any way.

Our results are listed in Table 1, where we see that noise elimination has better results for 6 and worse results for 2 out of the 17 datasets. One of these worse results can be explained because the reference data contains a very noisy signal that later becomes more stable, this causes an overestimation of the influence of noise and results in exact matches being found for the entire time series. More fine grained control of the noise parameter could likely correct this case. In total, by using noise elimination, we found 28 out of 30 anomalies, and made 56 wrong guesses in the process. In comparison, the original approach found 24 anomalies and had 80 wrong guesses. These results show that by using the noise elimination, anomalies

become generally more noticeable and false positives are reduced in the Matrix Profile, resulting in less time lost by the experts who diagnose these reports.

5 USE CASE: SEGMENTING TIME SERIES

Detecting changes in an underlying system based on sensor measurements has a wide range of applications, such as identifying different speakers in an audio recording, detecting system intrusion or data analysis in general. In this section we will perform time series segmentation using the Corrected Arc Curve (CAC), a technique based on the Matrix Profile. The CAC is calculated by the FLUSS algorithm or its on-line variant, the FLOSS algorithm, all are introduced in (Gharghabi et al., 2017).

The CAC is coined as a domain agnostic technique to perform semantic time series segmentation at super-human performance on realistic datasets and even on streaming data. Both FLUSS and FLOSS work by analyzing the Matrix Profile Index, which contains the index of the closest match for each subsequence in a time series. To calculate the CAC, the number of arcs (each spanning between a subsequence and their respective best match) are counted and divided by the expected amount of arcs if all matches were determined by uniform sampling over the entire time series. Assuming that homogeneous segments will display similar behavior and heterogeneous segments will not, a low ratio is seen as evidence of a change in the underlying system. The CAC is a vector of the same length as the Matrix Profile and is typically restricted to values between 0 and 1, the lower the value, the more evidence of a change in the underlying system.

5.1 Evaluation on PAMAP2 dataset

The PAMAP2 dataset (Reiss and Stricker, 2012) contains sensor measurements of 9 subjects performing a subset of 18 activities including: sitting, standing, walking, ironing and so on. The measurements are time series containing the output of a heart rate monitor and 3 inertial measurement units (IMU) placed on the chest, dominant wrist and dominant ankle of each subject. Each IMU measured 3-D acceleration data, 3-D gyroscope data and 3-D magnetometer data at around 100 Hz. The time series are annotated with the activity being performed by the subject or marked as a transition region in between activities. The duration of each activity varies greatly, but most activities last between 3 to 5 minutes.

Table 1: Results of anomaly detection using the Matrix Profile with and without noise elimination on the “realAWSCloud-watch” collection of the Numenta Anomaly Benchmark. Each model kept guessing until all anomalies were found or until 10 wrong guesses occurred. Bold entries indicate a better performance of one approach over the other. We see that by using noise elimination we can more easily find the annotated anomalies in most cases.

Dataset	#Anomalies	Without Noise Elimination		With Noise Elimination	
		Found Anomalies	Wrong Guesses	Found Anomalies	Wrong Guesses
ec2_cpu...e8d	2	0	10	2	0
ec2_cpu...a38	2	2	6	2	0
ec2_cpu...533	2	2	1	2	10
ec2_cpu...1ca	1	0	10	1	9
ec2_cpu...cc2	1	1	0	1	0
ec2_cpu...0cd	1	1	1	1	0
ec2_cpu...85a	0	0	0	0	0
ec2_cpu...f93	3	1	10	1	10
ec2_disk...3de	1	1	3	1	3
ec2_disk...644	3	3	10	3	10
ec2_netw...a54	1	1	0	1	0
ec2_netw...ac7	2	2	3	2	3
elb_reques...	2	2	10	2	0
grok_asg...	3	3	3	3	3
ii...NetworkIn	2	2	0	2	5
rds_cpu...c53	2	1	10	2	0
rds_cpu...b3b	2	2	3	2	3
Sum	30	24	80	28	56

The PAMAP2 dataset was used in (Yeh et al., 2017a), where the authors used the Matrix Profile to classify the activities in passive and active activities. Specifically, they note that the motif pairs in the passive actions are less similar and therefore less useful. We argue that motifs in passive actions, consisting of mainly flat signals, can also help us find structure in the data if we can remove the influence of the noise. We applied time series segmentation on the passive activities present in the PAMAP2 dataset, focusing on following activities: lying, sitting and standing. We picked these activities since their measurements display very few patterns in the data and they are consecutive activities for all subjects, meaning we did not have to introduce time-jumps in the data.

We considered subjects 1 to 8 of the dataset (subject 9 has no recordings of the relevant activities) and tested 2 cases: the transition from “lying” to “sitting” and the transition from “sitting” to “standing”. For each subject, we used the 3 accelerometer signals from the IMU placed on the chest of the subject, any missing data points were filled in using linear interpolation. We calculated the CAC with and without noise elimination using a subsequence length of 1000 (10 seconds). The standard deviation of the noise was estimated (without optimizing) by taking the 5th percentile of the standard deviations of all subsequences, similar to our approach in Section 4.

Figure 10: Three chest accelerometers of subject 6 from the PAMAP2 dataset. This extract contains 3 activities and one transition period. No clear patterns are discernible and many flat and noisy subsequences are present.

An example of the signals can be seen in Figure 10. We emphasize it is not our goal to build the optimal segmentation tool for this specific task, we simply want to evaluate the effect of the noise elimination on the CAC for sensor signals that contain flat but noisy subsequences.

There is one side effect of the noise cancellation that needs attention before calculating the CAC. After applying noise cancellation, many flat subsequences will have exact matches to other flat subsequences. However, since the Matrix Profile Index can only store a single match, the calculation order determines which match actually gets stored. This causes an unwanted pattern in the Matrix Profile indices, which contradicts the assumption of the CAC that the structure of matches is related to similar segments. Note

that this effect is already present in the normal Matrix Profile, but typically has little to no influence because multiple exact matches are extremely rare.

To solve this, we introduced reservoir sampling (Vitter, 1985) to the construction of the Matrix Profile Index. Reservoir sampling allows uniform sampling without replacement from a stream without knowing the size of the stream in advance. We implemented reservoir sampling so that the Matrix Profile Index no longer stores the first encountered best match, but a uniformly sampled instance of all matches with the lowest distance. This required us to store an additional vector of the same length as the Matrix Profile, keeping track of the number of exact matches that was encountered so far for each subsequence. Pseudo code to update the Matrix Profile and its indices is listed below.

```
# Matrix Profile and Index being updated
Input: mp, mpi
# Distances (e.g. from STOMP iteration)
Input: dists
# Indices corresponding to dists
Input: indices
# Counts exact matches per subsequence
Input: match_counts

better_indices = dists < mp
eql_indices = dists == mp AND finite(dists)
mp(better_indices) = dists(better_indices)
mpi(better_indices) = indices(better_indices)
match_counts(better_indices) = 1

match_counts(eql_indices) += 1
for i in eql_indices:
    if rand() < 1 / match_counts(i):
        mpi(i) = indices(i)

return (mp, mpi)
```

For both test cases (lying-sitting and sitting-standing), we calculated the CAC using the reservoir sampled Matrix Profile indices with and without noise elimination for each individual sensor. From the CAC, we derived a single activity-transition point by taking the location where the CAC is minimal. We considered 4 segmentations: one for each CAC of the 3 sensor channels and one obtained by combining (averaging) these individual CACs.

For scoring, we wish to reward splits on or near the transition periods as annotated in the data sets. Note that some transitions are instantaneous, while others consist of a transient period, as can be seen in Figure 10. We added a buffer margin of subsequence size m to the transitions, so each transition period is at least $2m$ wide. As score, we took the distance between the estimated transition location and the buffered transition period, normalized by the length of the series (containing both activities and the transition period).

Table 2: Score for the segmentation of the transition from “lying” to “sitting” using the 3 chest accelerometers from the PAMAP2 dataset for subjects 1 through 8, with and without noise elimination applied. Segmentation is performed using the CAC from a single sensor (C1, C2 and C3) and using the combined CAC. We see similar or better performance when applying noise elimination for all subjects except subject 1.

Subj.	Without NE				With NE			
	C1	C2	C3	Comb.	C1	C2	C3	Comb.
1	5.9	31.3	31.9	31.7	41.3	31.8	41.8	36.7
2	32.9	1.4	1.4	1.4	28.8	1.4	1.7	1.4
3	35.9	2.8	31.1	33.8	2.4	2.3	2.3	2.3
4	0.0	2.8	5.9	0.0	0.0	1.5	6.6	0.8
5	1.1	7.6	5.1	3.9	1.6	1.7	4.9	1.6
6	2.5	1.9	2.3	2.3	2.4	1.9	2.0	2.4
7	0.1	1.8	11.1	2.0	2.1	1.8	1.9	1.9
8	0.0	1.4	5.5	1.7	0.0	1.4	1.4	1.4
Avg.			9.32	9.61			7.71	6.07

Table 3: Score for the segmentation of the transition from “sitting” to “standing” using the 3 chest accelerometers from the PAMAP2 dataset for subjects 1 through 8, with and without noise elimination applied. Segmentation is performed using the CAC from a single sensor (C1, C2 and C3) and using the combined CAC. Overall, we see similar or better performance when applying noise elimination, except for the segmentation using the first channel for subject 1, 3 and 8.

Subj.	Without NE				With NE			
	C1	C2	C3	Comb.	C1	C2	C3	Comb.
1	32.5	0.0	3.6	2.2	38.7	0.0	3.7	2.2
2	36.5	37.2	36.4	37.0	7.1	30.0	32.7	29.2
3	10.0	30.2	43.1	30.2	43.2	14.0	43.7	30.2
4	7.8	1.9	1.1	1.2	0.7	2.0	1.3	1.3
5	13.1	0.0	28.5	10.6	13.3	1.0	1.2	1.0
6	36.1	36.6	26.9	36.6	23.3	3.4	26.5	3.2
7	43.1	38.0	16.5	16.5	43.4	1.6	0.0	1.6
8	2.3	1.0	24.8	1.0	21.1	0.0	16.5	1.0
Avg.			21.12	16.9			15.35	10.3

Pseudo code for this scoring function is listed below, a score will range from 0 to 100, where lower is better.

```
Input: est_split # Algorithmic estimate
Input: split_start, split_end # Ground truth
Input: n # Length of the time series
Input: b # Buffer for transition

if est_split < split_start - b:
    return ((split_start - b) - est_split)/n
elif est_split > split_end + b:
    return (est_split - (split_end + b))/n
else:
    return 0.
```

The results for segmentation on the transition from “lying” to “sitting” are listed in Table 2. We see that segmentation using the individual sensors as well as the combined approach provides similar or better results when using noise elimination for all subjects except for subject 1. The average score for the individual sensors improves from 9.32 to 7.71, a modest improvement corresponding to a gain of about 8 sec-

onds. The segmentation based on all 3 sensor series improves from 9.61 to 6.07, a gain of about 18.5 seconds. The results for subject 1 can be attributed to changes of the subjects body position near the start of the “lying” activity. This results in a lower-than-expected amount of matches near the start, causing the transition to be guessed too early. Note that both techniques have trouble with subject 1.

Table 3 lists the results for the transition from “sitting” to “standing”. Again, we see similar or improved results when applying noise elimination, except for 3 subjects using the first sensor series. Though results are worse compared to Table 2, the gain by using noise elimination is more significant. When using a single sensor, results on average improve from 21.12 to 15.35, corresponding to a gain of about 27 seconds. If segmentation uses all 3 sensors, results change from 16.9 to 10.3 on average, a gain of around 31 seconds.

6 CONCLUSION

In this paper we discussed techniques and applications related to the Matrix Profile. Our contribution consists of a method to remove the effects of Gaussian noise on the time series when calculating the Matrix Profile, without affecting the complexity of the underlying algorithm. This method is based on a statistical analysis of the effects of z-normalized noisy sequences on the Euclidean distance. The only requirement for this technique is to know the variance of the noise, which is an intuitive measure and can be easily estimated by manually extracting a *flat* but noisy segment from the time series.

As the Matrix Profile is widely usable for a variety of problems and across various domains, so is our technique. In this paper, we showed gains for anomaly detection and time series segmentation. Both cases were evaluated on public datasets containing real-word data and showed an improvement of the results. On the Numanta Anomaly Benchmark, we were able to retrieve more anomalies with less guesses, saving an operator valuable time. On the PAMAP2 dataset, we were able to more accurately predict transitions between passive activities. We focused on datasets containing flat and noisy segments, a subject that was not yet tackled in other Matrix Profile related literature.

Further work can be done on using a dynamic value for the noise estimation, for series where noise does not originate from measurement, but rather from the underlying process.

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